

Detection of the pumpkin flower to estimate its fruit position using a colour camera

Liangliang Yang*, Daichi Ando, Yohei Hoshino, Soichiro Suzuki, Ying Cao

**Laboratory of Bio-Mechatronics, Kitami Institute of Technology, 165, Koen-cho, Kitami-shi, 090-8507, Hokkaido, Japan*

yang@mail.kitami-it.ac.jp;

Abstract

The number of farmers has decreased dramatically, and the average age of the farmers is growing over 65 in Japan. Pumpkin is widely planted in Hokkaido, because there is almost no requirement of spraying and weeding management after transplanting. Therefore, many farmers want to expand the production of pumpkins. However, it is a heavy job to harvest the pumpkins. An autonomous harvesting machine for the pumpkin is required to be developed. The objective of this study is to find out the fruit position of the pumpkin, which is the basic technology for the auto-harvesting machine. Because the colour of the pumpkin fruits is similar to their leaves, the position of the fruits is difficult to be detected directly. In fact, the position of the pumpkin fruits is similar with the position of the flowers. Because the colour of the flowers and leaves are near yellow and green, respectively, the flowers could be detected by an image processing method. In this study, a colour camera was utilized to capture the images at an outdoor field. The colour space of the image was transformed from red, green and blue (RGB) to hue, saturation and value (HSV). The yellow flowers were detected in the HSV colour space. An experiment was conducted at an outdoor field of pumpkin in Hokkaido, Japan at daytime and evening. The results show that the method can detect out the flower correctly at both conditions, though some errors occur at the conditions when the colour of the background was similar with the flowers, or the colour of the flowers became white when the flowers were withered.

Keywords: pumpkin, auto-harvesting, flower detection, RGB image, HSV colour space.

Introduction

In order to find crops, weeds or any other plants in the fields for agriculture, vision systems were utilized mostly in recent researches. The vision system could be a colour, 3D, multi-wavelength or hyperspectral vision system. Iván et al. (2017) have utilized a colour camera to find the crop rows in a maize field in the straight and curved paths. The weeds and crops were not directly classified from the colour information because their colour were similar. Senthilnath et al. (2016) were using RGB images to detect tomatoes using an UAV mounted camera, and the results were expected to estimate the yield. Esmael et al. (2017) developed an image processing algorithm to recognize the cauliflower from weeds for weeds control. The research used a HSV method to identify the green cauliflower centre. And the HSV method was proved useful for the colour based classification method. Wang et al. (2012) have used colour images to develop a sweet cherry colour rating system. The colour information was utilized and the research was focused on how to remove the influence of the glaring reflections. Hyperspectral imaging was utilized (Okamoto et al., 2007) to identify weeds at a field for the weed control. The hyperspectral images consist of 240 wavebands of spectral information in the research. And thanks to the multi wavebands, the researchers could easily find out the difference of the sugar beet and weeds. But the hyperspectral camera was not became a first choice solution to classify the plants because of its high price. Wolfram et al. (2017) utilized a multi-wavelength laser line profile system for scanning the plants to yield 3D data as well as matched spectral reflectance for the plants. The research got a good classification for two crops that are carrots and corn salad. The depth camera or 3D camera (Tien et al., 2016) was utilized in a study for detect the red and bicoloured apples on tree using the colour and shape information.

Although the machine vision systems have been introduced to find the crops, weeds as well as fruits in the recent researches, how to find the objects of interests in the under controlled field conditions is still a challenging problem. There is not a normal form of algorithm to find all kinds of plants. It is necessary to design a special image processing algorithm to find the objective plants. In this study, the flowers of the pumpkin were expected to be identified from RGB images at an outdoor field. The position of the flowers was expected to be utilized for estimation of the position of the fruits. The position of the fruits could be applied to predict the yield and provide a pre-known information for harvesting.

Growing stages of the pumpkin

As shown in Fig. 1, a colour camera (GoPro™ 4, GoPro Inc., US) assembled on a tripod was utilized to monitor the growing condition of the pumpkin field in order to track the growth stages and figure out a good season to detect the flowers. A solar power panel was utilized to provide a power at daytime and save the power using a rechargeable battery for the night use. The total growth stage was recorded by this system over 24 hours one day for about 100 days from the day of transplanting to harvesting.

Figure 2 shows the growth stage images of the pumpkin, which are (a) first day after the transplanting, (b) start of quick growth of the vines on day 35 after the transplanting, (c) finish of the quick growth of the vines on day 46, (d) the flower fully open stage on day 59 and this stage is retain about a period of two weeks. It can be compared from Fig. 2 (d) and Fig. 2 (e) that the shape of the flowers are changed at day time and evening. The flowers are fully opened in the daytime at 10:00, while the flowerers are closed after 18:00. Therefore, it is easier to detect out the flower at daytime for the size is bigger. In this study, detection of the flower at the condition of evening was not given up because the working time could not be limited only to daytime for farmers who also work at evening.

Figure 1. The equipment for monitoring the growth

Figure 2. Typical scene of the pumpkin growth stages

Figure 3 shows a flower and a pumpkin fruit, it can be seen that the young pumpkin fruit is under the flower. Because as explained by Fig. 2, the opening flower stage is after the quick growth of the vines, the position of the fruits will not change because the length of vines have already decided. This is the reason why the position of the flowers can represent the position of the fruits.

Figure 3. A flower and a young fruit (around 17:00)

Detection method of the flower using colour images

1. Delete the soil area from the image

The colour of the dry soil is near yellow that is similar with the colour of the flowers. Therefore, the soil area need to be deleted at first in order to reduce the chance of misdetection of the soil area as flowers. It is known the reflection rate of the near infrared (NIR) for the soil and the growing plants are different. And this difference is normally utilized for showing the difference of the soil and plants (Iván et al., 2017). In this study, the RGB colour camera was utilized. The NIR band was not available for this study. Therefore, a special algorithm was going to be developed to detect the soil area without the assistant of the NIR image.

Figure 4 (a) ~ (d) illustrate four images that are dry soil, wet soil, green plant and yellow flower, respectively. In the colour images, it can be seen that the colour of the dry soil and the wet soil is different. However, as shown in Fig. 5, the colour of ration in red, green, blue bands for the soil they are almost similar no matter the soil is dry (around 180) or wet (around 95); while the colour of ratio for the plants at the three bands is different.

Therefore, in this study the soil and plants were classified through a normalized colour ratio factor I by Eq. (1),

$$I = (I_G + I_R) / I_B \quad (1)$$

where I_G , I_R and I_B are the colour of the green, red and blue bands, respectively.

Figure 4. Images of dry soil, leaf and flower

As shown in Fig. 5 (a) and (b), if the colour ratio I is less than 2.5 when the maximum value of the I_G , I_R and I_B are 255, the corresponding pixel of the image is considered as the soil. In Fig 5. (c), the value of I is also below 2.5 for the green leaf, therefore, the threshold 2.5 will delete some green leaves at the same time. If the ratio of green and red bands is consider the green leaf and soil can be classified. In this study, the green leaf was not going to be detected out, therefore the method of classifying the soil and the green leaf is not presented.

Figure 5. The colour of the RGB bands and colour ratio for the soil and plants

Figure 6 (a) shows the raw image with soil, plants, flowers and background, and Fig. 6 (b) shows the results after deleting the soil area. It can be seen from Fig. 6 (b) that the soil area is deleted. The left dark green leaf and flower will be classified in the HSV colour space. The image of Fig. 6(b) was filtered by using a mean filter with a smoothing window of 15 to 15 pixels in order to smooth the colour of the flowers.

(a) Raw image with soil and plants

(b) After deleting the soil area

Figure 6. The result of the deleting of the soil area

2. Detect the flower in the image

It can be seen from Fig 6. (b), the colour of the flower in the image is yellow. It is not easy to identify yellow colour in the RGB colour space. In this study, the HSV colour space was adopted to identify the flower. The HSV values are calculated from RGB image by Eq. (2),

$$\begin{aligned}
 V &= \max(I_R, I_G, I_B) \\
 S &= \begin{cases} (V - Vt) / V, & \text{if } V \neq 0 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\
 Vt &= V - \min(I_R, I_G, I_B) \\
 H &= \begin{cases} 60(I_G - I_B) / Vt & \text{if } V = I_R \\ 120 + 60(I_B - I_R) / Vt & \text{if } V = I_G \\ 240 + 60(I_R - I_G) / Vt & \text{if } V = I_B \end{cases}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where I_G , I_R and I_B are the colour in the green, red and blue bands; H , S , and V refer to the values of hue, saturation and value, respectively.

In the 8 bits images, the data range is between 0 and 255. Therefore, the HSV value from Eq. (2) are mapped to a new value at the range of 0 to 255 by Eq. (3),

$$\begin{cases} V = 255V \\ S = 255S \\ H = H / 2 \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

Figure 7 shows the image of Fig. 4 (c) and (d) in the HSV colour space, from which it can be seen that the H value of the flower (around 25) is different from the green leaf (around 70). The V was not utilized for classifying the colour, because the V value reflects the brightness of the image. The brightness was not utilized.

Therefore, the flower is identified by Eq. (4),

$$F = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } 15 > H > 35, \text{ AND } S > 25 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where H is the hue value of Eq. (2), if H is between the range of 15 to 35, the F will be 1, the corresponding area in the image will be considered as the flower, otherwise the corresponding area will be considered as the leaf. The S value is limited to larger than 25

The result of the flower detection is shown in Fig. 8. The noise in the image of Fig. 8 (a) was removed by filter the size of the possible flower by using two times of erode and dilate operation. And the window size was defined as 11 by 11 in the filter process. The final results is shown in Fig. 8 (b), the detected flower is shown in the red area. It can be seen that the flower is possible to be detected by using the image from a colour camera. And the image processing method designed in this study is effective on detect the yellow flower.

Figure 7. HSV values of leaf and the flower in Figure 4

(a) The white areas are the possible flowers, the small points are noise points

(b) Remove the noise points of (a) and the flowers are shown in the red area

Figure 8. Flower detection result

Results and discussion

In order to verify the method that proposed using the colour camera for detecting the pumpkin flower, an experiment was carried out to grab images at an outdoor pumpkin field in Hokkaido at day time (before 17:00) and evening (18:00~19:00).

Figure 9 shows the identifying result at day time, from which it can be seen that at daytime the flowers are correctly detected and no non-flower objects are detected as flowers. In this figure, there are totally 9 flowers, but only 5 flowers are marked as flower. The reason for the flower 6~9 are not marked as flower is that the colour is not yellow. In addition, as shown in Fig. 10 (a), the flower can be detected correctly even at evening if the colour is yellow.

Figure 9. Detection result at daytime

As shown in Fig. 10 (b) and (c), at the condition that the colour of the flower is distorted from yellow to white when the flower is withered, no matter at daytime or evening the flower cannot be perfectly detected. There are two kind errors for detection of the flowers: the first is that flower is not identified (first error); the second is that the not-flower is identified as flower (second error).

(a) Evening

(b) First error

(c) Second error

Figure 10. Detection results at different conditions

The results are explained in table 1. From this table it can be seen that the error is mostly at the evening condition. It is considered that at the evening the colour of the images is easier to be distorted from yellow to white; and as explained in Fig. 2 (e), the flower closed at evening. Therefore, it is better to grab images at daytime for identifying the pumpkin flower. Totally, there is only one error detection for the second error and 12 error detection for the first error when the total number of the images is 53.

Appendix A shows the examples of the detection results of this study. The flowers are classified to four groups: group 1 is the flowers that are easy for human to detect, but error detected by PC; group 2 is the flowers that are difficult for human to detect and error detected by PC; group 3 is the flowers that are easy for human to detect and correctly detected by PC; group 4 is that the flowers are difficult for human to detect but can be detected by PC. The reason of the results for group 4 is that the detection algorithm in this study is only using the colour information that does not rely on the brightness of the image, therefore if the colour of the flower is not distorted as shown group 1 and group 2 the flower will be correctly detected even at bad illumination conditions.

Table 1. Results of the detection of the flowers

Condition	First error	Second error
Daytime	3	0
Evening	9	1

Conclusions

This study focused on detection of the pumpkin flower at an outdoor condition. A colour camera was utilized to capture the pumpkin flower images. The yellow flower was detected in the HSV colour space. The experiment was conducted in a field in Hokkaido, Japan at daytime and evening. The experiment results indicate that the flowers can be correctly detected at the daytime as well as evening. However, some area of the image, which did not have any flowers were detected as flower image, when its colour was similar to yellow. There were 53 images of the flowers for testing the image processing method. The proposed method correctly detected 40 images. Most of the errors were at the condition that the flowers were withered, and the colour was distorted from yellow to white. And there is space to detect the white colour flowers for additional research.

References

- Esmael H, Brian McG, Martin G, Edward J 2017. Automatic crop detection under field conditions using the HSV colour space and morphological operations, *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 133: 97–107.
- Iván D, García-Santillán Martín M, José M Guerrero, Gonzalo P 2017. Automatic detection of curved and straight crop rows from images in maize fields, *Biosystems Engineering* 156: 61–79.
- Lamb DW, Schneider DA, Trotter MG, Schaefer MT, Yule IJ 2011. Extended-altitude, aerial mapping of crop NDVI using an active optical sensor: A case study using a Raptor™ sensor over wheat, *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 77(1): 69–73.
- Okamoto H, Murata T, Kataoka T, Hata S-I 2007. Plant classification for weed detection using hyperspectral imaging with wavelet analysis. *Weed Biol. Manage* 7(1): 31–37.
- Senthilnath J, Akanksha D, Manasa K, Ramesh KN, Gautham A, Omkar SN 2016. Detection of tomatoes using spectral-spatial methods in remotely sensed RGB images captured by UAV, *Biosystems Engineering* 146: 16–32.
- Tien Thanh Nguyen, Koenraad Vandevoorde, Niels Wouters, Erdal Kayacan, Josse G. De Baerdemaeker, Wouter Saeys 2016. Detection of red and bicoloured apples on tree with an RGB-D camera, *Biosystems Engineering* 146: 33–44.
- Wang Q, Wang H, Xie L, Zhang Q 2012. Outdoor colour rating of sweet cherries using computer vision, *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 87: 113–120.
- Wolfram Strothmann, Arno Ruckelshausen, Joachim Hertzberg, Christian Scholz, Frederik Langsenkamp 2017. Plant classification with In-Field-Labeling for crop/weed discrimination using spectral features and 3D surface features from a multi-wavelength laser line profile system, *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 134: 79–93.

Appendix A. Examples of the detection results

Group 1: Easy for human, error detected by PC

1

2

3

Group 2: Difficult for human, error detected by PC

1

2

3

4

5

6

7

8

9

Group3: Easy for human, correct detected by PC

Group 4: Difficult for human, correct detected by PC

1

2

3

4

5

6

7

8

9

10

11

12

13

14

15